

Studies in Ring Formation.

By

ANUKUL CHANDRA SIRCAR AND PRAN KUMAR DE.

The investigation may conveniently be divided into three parts, A, B and C.

A. Attempts to prepare *p*-Diphenylene.

For substances like benzidine or naphthalene Kaufler (*Annalen*, 1907, 351, 151) proposed a theory according to which the two phenyl groups in the molecule of benzidine do not lie on one plane—the valency joining them being not fixed in space, but in an oscillatory condition.

Hence the two amino groups are sometimes near one another, as shown in (I), and should together have the effect of an *ortho*-diamine. According to this conception diphenyl becomes a derivative of a hypothetical substance, namely, *p*-diphenylene:—

This substance is unknown. Dobbie, Fox and Gauge (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 99, 683) have prepared *o*-diphenylene.

It is obvious that Kaufler's conception of diphenyl would be supported if the parent hydrocarbon, namely *p*-diphenylene were obtained. From a study of the literature of the subject, it appears that no attempt had been made in a plausible direction for the preparation of *p*-diphenylene.

Ullmann (*Annalen*, 1904, 332, 38) and others have shown that iodo-compounds are better adapted than chloro- or bromo-compounds for the preparation of polycyclic substances from mono-cyclic ones and that finely divided copper is suitable for the elimination of halogen atoms. The authors thought that if benzidine has the "butterfly" constitution suggested by Kaufler, then *p*:*p'*-di-iodo-diphenyl must be similar, and that on treatment with copper powder might yield *p*-diphenylene.

Repeated attempts to eliminate the iodine atoms in *p*:*p'*-di-iodo-diphenyl were unsuccessful.

p-Di-iodobenzene was next tried, the iodine atoms in that substance also being favourably situated for the formation of *p*-diphenylene,

The results obtained were as disappointing as before. In one experiment a small amount of a white crystalline substance was isolated. But on examination it was found to be only *p*:*p'*-di-iodo-diphenyl, so that only one of the iodine atoms was eliminated from each molecule.

Thus attempts to prepare *p*-diphenylene have so far been unsuccessful.

B. *Attempts to prepare Derivatives of p : p'-Diazophenylene.*

Kaufler (*loc. cit.*) has said that various other types of $p : p'$ -diamino compounds *viz.*, $p : p'$ -diamino-diphenyl methane and $p : p'$ -diamino-stilbene behave in the same way as benzidine, *i.e.*, show the properties of an *ortho*-diamine. From the similarity in the constitution of $p : p'$ -diamino-stilbene and of $p : p'$ -diamino-azo-benzene there seemed to be no reason why the latter substance should not also behave like an *ortho*-diamine. The present part of the investigation is concerned with that problem and with attempts to prepare derivatives of $p : p'$ -diazophenylene. The problem was attacked in the same way as was followed in the case of benzidine by Kaufler (*loc. cit.*), Cain and Micklethwaite (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1437) and Turner and his colleagues (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1495; 1917, 111, 1; 1920, 117, 1140).

Bandrowski (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 1181) prepared diphthalyl benzidine. Gustav Koller (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2880), by the actions of phthalic anhydride on benzidine, prepared a phthalyl derivative which was found to be different from Bandrowski's compound. Kaufler, by a determination of the molecular weight of Koller's phthalyl derivative as well as of the compound obtained by the action of oxalyl chloride on benzidine, proved that in either case they were formed by the condensation of one molecule of each of the reacting substances, and brought forward this as an argument in favour of the *o*-diamine

formula of benzidine. Another proof of the advantages of Kauler's formula was brought forward by Cain and Micklethwaite, who found that *o*-diketones, like benzil and glyoxal, condense with benzidine to give compounds of the type,

However, attempt to repeat Cain and Micklethwaite's works made by Ferriss and Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1920, 117, 1140) and by the authors were unsuccessful.

Turner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1496) tried the reaction of acetylacetone on benzidine in the expectation that if benzidine possesses an *ortho*-diamine formula the two ketonic groups of acetylacetone will condense with one molecule of benzidine to yield a compound of the type

The results obtained were, however, quite different from those expected.

It has now been found that phthalic anhydride does not react with *p*:*p'*-diamino-azo-benzene; phthalyl chloride reacts with it to form a diphthalyl derivative, *i.e.*, two molecules of phthalyl chloride react with one molecule of *p*:*p'*-diamino-azo-benzene. Owing to the extreme insolubility in all organic solvents of the condensation product of oxalyl chloride and *p*:*p'*-diamino-azo-benzene, it could not be decided whether it was formed by the condensation of one molecule of oxalyl chloride with one molecule of *p*:*p'*-diamino-azo-benzene or by the condensation of two molecules of each of the two substances.

Glyoxal or benzil could not be made to react with *p*:*p'*-diamino-azo-benzene. Acetylacetone reacts with the

diamino-compound in the same way as it does with benzidine (Turner, *loc. cit.*) and an azo-quinoline derivative is formed.

Thus attempts to prepare derivatives of *p*: *p'*-diazophenylene have also been so far unsuccessful.

C. Action of Aldehydes on Benzidine and p: *p'*-Diaminoazo-benzene.

A characteristic reaction of the *ortho*-diamine is the readiness with which they condense with aldehydes to form iminazolones. The action of anisaldehyde on benzidine and that of salicylaldehyde and of resorcyaldehyde on *p*: *p'*-diamino-azo-benzene has now been tried. In every case two molecules of the aldehyde are found to react with one molecule of the diamino compound and it was found that there was not the slightest tendency towards iminazolone formation.

Conclusion.

The results obtained so far all go against Kaufler's formula for benzidine and similar *p*: *p'*-diamino-substances.

EXPERIMENTAL.

An intimate mixture of *p*-di-iodobenzene (9.30 g.) and finely divided copper powder (Natur Kupfer C, 17.5 g.) was heated at 300–330° for three hours, after which time the copper was found to have lost its lustre. The contents of the tube were taken out and weighed; separate portions were treated respectively with acetic acid, ether, alcohol, chloroform, benzene and nitrobenzene. It was found that nothing was extracted by organic solvents.

A portion of the product was boiled with concentrated hydrochloric acid for five minutes and the mixture was filtered. On making the filtrate alkaline a reddish looking heavy precipitate was obtained in good yield. On examination it was found to contain copper and was therefore not further examined.

The above experiment was repeated several times at different temperatures, but with no better result.

2:4:2':4'-Tetramethyl-azo-quinoline.

4:4'-Diamino-azo-benzene (0.55 g.) was warmed with acetylacetone (1.5 g.) until everything went into solution. The solution was then boiled for two minutes more. On cooling a crystalline solid separated. This was collected and recrystallised from alcohol as shining red prisms (m. p. 192–193°). It is soluble in alcohol and acetic acid, insoluble in water and dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found: N = 16.12, 15.86. $C_{22}H_{20}N_4$ requires N = 16.47 per cent.).

Diphthalyl benzidine was obtained as shining yellow needles on adding phthalyl chloride (2 g.) to a solution of benzidine (1 g.) in nitrobenzene (40 c. c.). On examination it was found to be identical with the compound obtained by Bandrowski (*loc. cit.*).

Diphthalyl-4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene.

A solution of 4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene (1 g.) in the least quantity of nitrobenzene was treated with phthalyl chloride (2 g.) when at once a black precipitate appeared. It was boiled for half an hour when the colour changed from black to brown. The solid was then filtered, washed with ether and crystallised from nitrobenzene: light-brown needles, m. p. above 300°.

It is insoluble in ether, acetic acid and alcohol. (Found: N=12.32. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$ requires N=11.85 per cent.).

Oxalyl-4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene.

A solution of 4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene (1 g.) in cold nitrobenzene (80 c.c.) was treated with oxalyl chloride (2 c.c.) when at once a reddish precipitate appeared. The solution was then boiled for half an hour and the colour of the precipitate changed to light yellow. It was purified by boiling successively with nitrobenzene and pyridine and filtering hot when the substance remained on the filter paper as light yellow particles, m. p. above 300°. It is insoluble in organic liquids. (Found: N=20.93. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$ requires N=21.05 per cent.).

Benzidine-bis-(p-methoxy-phenyl-azo-methine).

Benzidine (1 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (60 c.c.) and the solution was cooled to 0°. It was then treated with anisaldehyde (0.73 g.) and a light yellow precipitate appeared gradually. After half an hour the mixture was

filtered. The solid product was crystallised from nitrobenzene: shining light yellow plates, m. p. 246-48°.

It is very slightly soluble in alcohol, more so in acetic acid and nitrobenzene. It is readily hydrolysed to benzidine and the aldehyde on warming with dilute hydrochloric acid. (Found: N=7.09. $C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2$ requires N=6.67 per cent.)

Azo-benzene-p : p'-bis-(hydroxy-phenyl-azo-methine).

A cold solution of 4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene (0.5 g.) in alcohol (60 c.c.) was treated with salicylaldehyde (0.5 g.) when at once a reddish crystalline precipitate appeared. It was filtered and recrystallised from nitrobenzene: light brown shining plates, m. p. 265°.

It is insoluble in alkali, dilute hydrochloric acid and in alcohol, soluble in warm acetic acid and nitrobenzene. (Found: N=13.36. $C_{26}H_{20}N_4O_2$ requires N=13.33 per cent.)

Azo-benzene-p : p'-bis-(3 : 4-dihydroxy-phenyl-azo-methine).

A solution of 4:4'-diamino-azo-benzene (0.5 g.) in hot alcohol (60 c.c.) was treated with resorcyaldehyde (0.5 g.). After boiling for half an hour the solution was allowed to cool when a reddish-brown crystalline precipitate gradually separated. This was filtered, washed with warm alcohol and dried. It begins to darken at about 250° but does not melt below 270°. It is readily hydrolysed by cold alkali. It is slightly soluble in alcohol, readily soluble in acetic acid. (Found: N=12.62. $C_{26}H_{20}N_4O_4$ requires N=12.39 per cent.)